

Urban Tourism and Challenges: A Study of Varanasi City

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Abstract

Tourism in 19th century itself, was considered as one of the basic human needs, thereby becoming the necessity of society. Cities have always been tourist destinations from a cultural-historical nature to the now more modern form of business and medical tourism. As a result of this transformation, a new concept appeared; Urban Tourism. Now Urban Agglomerations are the leading destinations. Tourism being an important source of income for many developing countries, had been the most affected industry due to the COVID 19 pandemic. It has developed social and medical emergencies along with profound adverse consequences on the global economy. Varanasi being a tourist destination from time immemorial, faces the challenges of Urban Tourism and also the setbacks due to the pandemic. Rampant urbanization and an increase in population has adversely affected the quality of life. Being one of the largest agglomerations of the Uttar Pradesh state, the city needs to re-build tourism after the pandemic to a more sustainable pattern. This paper is a critical analysis of tourism in Varanasi, its problems and looking at most appropriate post – pandemic perspective for Urban Tourism. This is a descriptive study depending on the synthesis of early literature and sources of published news and reports related to tourism management.

KEY-WORDS: Urban Tourism, Urbanization, Sustainable Tourism, COVID 19, Carrying Capacity, Digital Tourism, Pro-poor Tourism.

Introduction

Tourism contains the activities of people, travelling to different places, which is outside their habitual environment for business, medical or simply leisure purposes, with staying there for not more than one continuous year. The definition given by Humzikhor and Krapf about the concept of tourism, which was subsequently adopted by the International Association of Scientific Experts in Tourism (AIEST) involves three distinct elements of Tourism; involvement of travel by Non-residents, stay of temporary nature in the area and stay not connected with any activity involving earnings. According to Zivadin Joviac, 'It is a social movement with a view to rest, diversion and satisfaction of cultural needs.'

Manila Declaration on World Tourism of 1980 talks about its direct effects on the social, cultural, educational and economic sectors of national societies and on their international relations. Tourism rather than being a separate discipline, overlaps with other activities, interests and processes. The study of tourism by just a demographic point of view is now a thing of the past. In the start of the 21st century itself, we witness tourism which is more socially and politically driven phenomenon. The COVID 19 pandemic has been quite obstreperous event, with huge impacts on tourism. Tourism has also been one of the causes of the pandemic and hence so badly affected. International tourists' arrival, saw a decline by 74 percent in 2020 when compared to the last year. Many developing countries witnessed a 80-

90 percent downfall in tourists' arrival. UNCTAD reports, see a pre-covid scenario for tourism sector by 2023 or later.

India holds an enviable position with 5,000 years of history, geographical diversity, heritage and culture. The country has been stereotyped for it, basically being a cultural destination. A new paradigm is indeed in progress where we see more diversified form of tourism. A lot of problems which deaccelerates the country's tourism industry are lack of hygiene and comfortable accommodations, absence of an information system, lack of integrated tourism promotion programmes, challenges in managing urban infrastructure, etc. there are many environmental and socio-economic factors affecting tourism which further reduces the desired quality of tourism.

Urban Tourism

Urban agglomerations provide for and extensive and assorted collection of various historical, cultural, architectural, social, natural and as well as manmade experiences. Thus, a type of tourism activity emerges, Urban Tourism, in an urban space with non-agricultural based economy being the innate characteristic of the region. Urban Agglomerations being the leading destinations for urban tourism are more affected by pandemic because most cases of infections and deaths are accumulated in cities, badly affecting the city's attractiveness. Varanasi, owing to its rich tradition, attracts more than 60 lakh domestic and international tourists each year. The peak season is regarded as October-March with tourist inflow being 60

percent of the total domestic tourist coming in a year while for the foreign tourist it is 71 percent. The average stay is 2-3 days for both domestic and foreign tourists. All the important (Hindu) festivals like Dev Deepawali, Ganga Mahotsav, Ram Leela are celebrated between October-March. The city Ghats, historical and cultural attractions, religious significance, philanthropic significances, makes it even more attractive to the tourists. Most domestic tourists are from Bihar, West Bengal, Madhya Pradesh and other parts of Uttar Pradesh, while the majority of foreign tourists are from Sri Lanka and Japan (JNNURM).

Tourism is a combination of inter related industries like hotel, restaurant, transport, etc. also there is backward and forward linkages and cross-sectoral synergies with sectors like agriculture, horticulture, poultry, transport, construction, handicrafts, etc which leads to large scale employment generation and poverty alleviation. The lively city of Varanasi, which never stopped, came to a standstill during the pandemic, when the ghats were deserted and its revered temples were closed, times which even the eldest of the generations here have seen for the first time in their lives. The city paid the price of the pandemic not only economically but also physically and emotionally. Apart from the pandemic there are many factors which effect the city's tourism like, historical and cultural factors, weather conditions, accessibility, amenities: both manmade and natural, socio-economic factors, etc. which needs the attention of the policy makers. Being a cultural and historical destination with tourism, the second largest sector of the city, Varanasi's economy, also comprises of the priests, hotels, the florists and tour guides. The flower markets of the city have seen a downfall, during the COVID times with almost all the major temples closed, which badly affected the farmers associated with floral farming. There were times when the flower wholesale markets at Bansphatak and Englishia Line saw a huge gap in their production and sales. Clearly the pandemic affected the economy at large of this sector. With the lockdowns imposed, major rituals performed at the ghats like the Ganga Aarti which attract tourists all over the world, came to a halt; greatly effecting the hotel industry. There has been a major occupational shift among the tourists guides as their scope of earning was limited to the commissions they make at several stages of booking and travel. The city needs to re-build its tourism along a sustainable form, for the future.

Challenges Of Urban Tourism In Varanasi

In their analysis of tourist satisfaction in Varanasi through important performance analysis, Sujoy Vikram Singh and Naresh Tanwar concluded that for the tourists in Varanasi, clean environment and hygiene were the critical issues. Many schemes like Swachh Bharat Abhiyan, HRIDAY, PRASAD needs to be effectively executed in order to maintain positive reviews, the Destination Management Organizations (DMO's) should invest in improving the core facilities like maintaining pedestrian pathways, enhancing the role of Tourist Information Centres for there are discrepancies in the information present at the destination and at online sources. Placement of direction and signage boards at every tourist place, cleanliness and maintenance of public convenience facilities were other issues.

The COVID 19 pandemic has caused great havoc to the world economy. Hygiene and health conditions have become of utmost importance for tourists travel decisions. The pandemic has certainly provided the policy makers to think about the challenges that lay ahead for Urban Tourism. According to the Tourist Statistics Department, Uttar Pradesh, 2017, Varanasi ranks eighth among top sixteen places in U.P. according to domestic tourist visits and according to foreign visits it ranks third with Sarnath at second place.

Uncontrolled Urbanization –

Varanasi ranks 18th in terms of population in the state. The percentage share of urban population in the district is 43.4 as against 22.3 of the population in urban areas of the state. Varanasi district has population density of 2,395 persons per square kilometre which is more than the state average 829 persons per square kilometre. Total population of the district is 36,76,841 in which urban population is 15,97,051 comprising 43.4 percent of the total population.

There is a huge gap in opportunities and facilities in some of the areas of the city. Varanasi witnesses a recent socio-economic growth and modernization in all fields of activities which has brought radical changes like, spontaneous building constructions (both legal and illegal), consequent landscape alteration and downgrading. The components responsible for urbanization in Varanasi are socio-cultural and religious attractions, being an ancient educational centre, trade and commerce, a tourist centre, rural-urban transformation, medical hub. The main problem of urbanization is that it's concentrated in some particular areas only. Speedy growth of population over the last two

decades has rendered the central part of the city over crowded.

Managing Urban Infrastructure –

The urban infrastructure system is managed using certain social and technical principles, providing basic services for the urban habitat. The services like water, energy, transportation are the foundations of any city and a lack of sustainability in any one sector can lead to a havoc for the whole ecosystem. Hence, governments should aim for sustainable, more resilient and efficient infrastructural development. Of course, the pre-existing unplanned infrastructure, doesn't help with the further advancements and hinders further development but irrational infrastructural development leads to cities historicity damage. Already Varanasi is a congested place with the main city still not developed enough to tackle traffic jams and crowding. Footpath erosion, problem of increased littering, sensitive habitat destroyed and converted into hotels and stay rooms have become quite common in the city. Infrastructure and real estate development are growing very rapidly in cities and in the outskirts, apartment culture is keeping pace with the metro cities. And this advancement of human civilization has put serious questions on the safe use of natural resources. The forest cover is awfully low, accounting for not more than 5 percent of the total area. In addition, there has been an exceptional rise in built-up area, which has grown by 53 percent. This signifies a spree in construction activity, mainly on account of increasing demand for residential accommodation and expansion of commercial activities. Agricultural land has gone down by 5.3 percent. The area under vegetation cover and wasteland, too, has declined by 20 percent and 28 percent respectively.

Carrying Capacity –

UNWTO defines carrying capacity 'the maximum number of people that may visit a tourist destination at the same time, without causing destruction of the physical, economic, socio-cultural, environment and an unacceptable decrease in the quality of visitors satisfaction'. The demand of the present is to probe into possible theoretical solutions for managing not only the resources but also the entire city facilities like, limiting the access, firm restrictions on certain activities, enforcing rules and regulations, providing more information and educating the masses. Tourism sector needs to re-analyse, keeping in view the change in travellers' behaviour post-pandemic and to

redefine future tourism by more sustainable means.

Even a modest but unregulated rush of tourists raises the wages of labour, prices of land and articles of daily use in the tourist region. More demand and less supply of water and power, shared by both the tourists and local residents, creates shortages- the worse sufferers are always the local people. Tourist carrying capacity of the city needs to be matched to the growing tourist traffic and the increase in the number of incoming job seekers to check these problems. There is a need to support facilities and also provide opportunities to support higher income segments. Presently the sewerage system of the city is inadequate with 70 percent area of uncovered sewer system and discharge of untreated sewage in open drains, into Ganga. This already drastic scenario with its inadequate carrying capacity poses a threat to city's environment, with an add on of large tourist influx.

Effects On Environment –

A declining bio-diversity as a result of all sorts of human activity, came to light in the latest United Nations report on assessment of ecosystems. How sensitive is the tourist industry to all the adverse changes in environment if it is not properly conserved is a burning question? Nature's beauty, wild life, cultural attractions and ecology needs to be conserved in order to protect the very resource base of tourism from destruction. The city came into limelight in 2015, when Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) data highlighted that the city didn't have even a 'single good air quality day' that year. In fact, Varanasi is among the 43 critically polluted zones across the country. Data revealed that pollution levels in Varanasi were 20 times more than WHO's standards. The city's air quality was found to be more toxic than in Delhi.

A good quality and sufficient quantity of water is equally essential for keeping alive the tourist industry. It is required for many direct and indirect uses, which grows on increasing as the number of tourists increases. The shortage and pollution of water adds to the prevailing insanitary conditions and the diseases in densely populated areas of the city. An unregulated inflow of visitors to tourist places in the vicinity are so affected by such conditions that they may decide to keep away from the city, the next time. The city is threatened by groundwater extinction, shrinkage of surface water and its contamination, polluted air and enormous land pressure. Also, the city is producing huge amounts of municipal solid waste and due to the absence of a proper

dumping ground, it is being disposed in low-lying areas in every nook and corner of the city as well as at the banks of the River Ganga, Varuna and Assi or in and around ponds and wells in the city.

The combined effect of low flow and discharge of polluted effluents into the Ganga has caused severe deterioration in the quality of water. A latest report of the Ministry of Environment Forest and Climate Change on the Ganga River shows that the stretch of Allahabad to Varanasi has more than 6 mg/l dissolved oxygen and huge faecal coliform, which implies that it is not suitable for even bathing purposes.

Effect On Local Culture –

Varanasi being basically a cultural tourism destination witnesses an encounter between foreign tourists and the local people. It's a clash between two sets of cultures observed at a number of tourist places here. There is only a commercial relation between the tourists and their hosts just as is between the sellers and buyers of goods and services in the market. Treating local people as objects of curiosity by the tourists cause irritation among the former. Tourists are generally members of a high consumption society of pleasure seekers landing in the midst of society suffering from wants. Youths of the host area suffer from cultural alienation by imitating the behaviour pattern of the tourists and losing the hold of their family traditions. It is the major negative impact of urban tourism, more harmful in the stages of early growth. Increasing number of modern restaurants and clubs alongside the Ghats, are attracting tourists but adversely affecting the culture of this ancient city.

Tourism is generally the spread of local culture amongst the travellers, but this has some adverse effects on the local residents also. High end café, bars and clubs are introduced to please and welcome a certain group of tourists in the city, which is mainly concentrated along the banks of the river Ganga, leading to unnecessary congestion and pollution also. To attract western tourists and create a favourable environment for them the local cuisines and entertainment hubs take a back seat and get further neglected. The local culture is currently thriving to survive against this manicured tourism set up. Many new starts ups and cultural organizations and groups work steadily to keep the originality of tradition and culture of a region alive. Administrative support for these groups can bring a good balance between tourism for commerce and tourism for cultural experience. Tourism indeed acts as a

catalyst for economic growth but there is a need of balance between economic and cultural prosperity.

Health And Hygiene –

Only 32 percent of the households are covered by the sewerage network in the city. The remaining is covered via septic tanks and pits; and rest are not covered at all. 18 percent of the city's population has no access to toilets, either independent or shared. Also, the existing sewerage network is very old and in need of repair. The carrying capacity of the sewerage lines is adversely affected due to garbage dumping and a heavy footfall of tourists lead to pressure on this existing scenario.

Despite much remaining unknown about the future of travel post COVID 19, the world is seeing emerging trends about health and hygiene in travel and tourism concerning traveller booking behaviour and resident sentiment. This means that the city's tourism managers and policy makers need to re-think, re-build and reposition the city's focus on health and hygiene accordingly. In light of growing health and safety concerns, travellers will increasingly turn to authorities they trust for timely and accurate information ahead of and during their travels.

Lack Of Integrated Tourism Development Programme –

The National Heritage City Development and Augmentation Yojana (HRIDAY), a central sector scheme of the Government of India, was launched on 21st January 2015 with the aim of bringing together urban planning, economic growth and heritage conservation in an inclusive manner and with the objective of preserving the heritage character of the city. The mission period of the scheme ended on 31st March, 2019. The scheme has supported development of core heritage linked civic infrastructure projects which includes revitalization of urban infrastructure for areas around heritage, religious, cultural and tourism assets of the cities. These initiatives include development of water supply, sanitation, drainage, waste management, approach roads, footpaths, street lights, tourist conveniences, electricity wiring, landscaping and other citizen services.

Mostly tourism is considered as a way of commercial engagement, leading towards profit for a state in economy. Mostly this is done by establishing commercial zones, instead of promoting and preserving the places of sightseeing or of historical importance. Some other times, a certain zone is overly developed to either compensate for the lack of commercial

prosperity in the other spots. For example, if city has x, y, z places having good amount of footfall, but only x has the capacity to convert the footfall into commerce, that spot would be given more focus and would be developed more than other ones. The Vishwanath Corridor is one such place which has been overly developed for the tourists while many other tourist places are struggling to survive without lack of attention. The Varanasi Smart City Mission aims to provide for the aspirations and requirements of the people, while also developing the institutional, physical, social and economic infrastructure to build a complete urban ecosystem. The objectives of the mission are to provide basic infrastructure, improve and enhance the quality of life, ensure and strive for clean and sustainable environment, apply smart solutions, set examples which can be replicated within as well as outside the smart city, so as to enhance the creation of more smart cities. The Heritage Development Plan for Varanasi, aims to regulate its heritage zones, conserving the built cultural heritage, provide and interface of heritage management with spatial planning to come up with a regulatory framework for development that is heritage sensitive.

Lack of resources, lack of co-operation between various stakeholders like public officers, business community, locals, politicians, industry fragmentation, no volunteer enthusiasm, leadership skills efforts from individuals have led to increased problems of urban tourism in the city. The Varanasi's City Development Plan (CDP) lacks the survey and understanding of the present ground realities faced by the city. The pandemic has indeed made the governments to work in a more collaborated manner at all levels, thus emphasizing on the need of more consolidated tourism policies for faster recovery of the sector; with the objective to have more instinctive and pliable policies which is able to adapt to changes faster, a sturdy safety and health policy issues and crisis management.

Re-Building Tourism

The UN Secretary General, Antonio Guterres says 'As we restart and recover from the pandemic, UNWTO, has a key role in rethinking tourism and its interactions with our societies, economies and natural resources and ecosystems'. The pandemic driven slowdown has given the opportunity to uplift more revolutionary changes in the sector with new models, opening up new destinations and thriving for sustainable tourism patterns. Also, the pandemic has provided for new approaches to be adopted for maintaining the overall balance

of environmental, social and economic results of the tourism. This can be achieved by introducing new technologies, executing more of green recuperating strategies and shifting to more resilient policy and business practices. The future of the tourism industry definitely sees a paradigm shift, due to the pandemic and the G20Tourism ministers in the Diriyah Communique assured the governments to work together for the cause and support of sustainable retrieval of the tourism sector. The disruption brought about by the pandemic has provided the policy makers to grasp the opportunity and reset the economy of this sector, with stronger sustainable base. Since this sector is the most affected by the pandemic, it's the top most priority of the international institutions like, UN, World Bank, WTO to revive the economy of this sector.

Sustainable Tourism –

Varanasi needs a serious re-consideration about its tourism industry according to sustainable pattern. On the one hand flowing of more than 5 million tourists per year, and on the other hand inadequacy and inefficiency of infrastructure for welcoming the tourists, lead to an increased unsustainable condition

The term 'sustainability' emerged in 90's and gradually entered to economic and political context; until 1997, there was not established a relation between tourism and sustainable development. It became introduced for the first time in 'Agenda 21' for the 'travel and tourism industry' which draws its principles from the 1992 UN Conference on Environment and Development. 'Agenda 21' presents tourism as a factor in order to achieve promotion of quality of life and economic flourishing of the local people. Sustainable tourism is taking charge of all the resources in a way that economic and social needs are fulfilled along with maintaining the cultural and biological diversity of the region, intact. The objective of tourism is development of tourism without any ruinous effect on natural, historical, cultural or social resources in order to improve economic growth and to respect to customs of host community.

Indicators of sustainable tourism include controlled growth of tourism industry, capacity of surveying number of tourists according to possibility and infrastructure of place, encouragement of local communities in participating in tourism development in the name of improvement of the economic status of local communities and preserving natural resources. There are certain

barriers on adopting sustainable practices like; lack of financial resources, lack of knowledge/awareness, lack of available staff, etc.

Urban Infrastructure –

The COVID19 pandemic emphasized the need to re-consider the role of free spaces in Metropolitan areas as well as their accessibility. Challenges including crowding and impacts by over tourism on public free spaces will require joint strategies involving all public and private institutions (including local communities) responsible for the maintenance of green and blue free spaces. Strategically planned network of natural and semi-natural areas, which absorb precipitation and reduce water run-off even maintaining their retention function during heavy rainfall events. These measures primarily benefit the local population, but there may also be positive synergies for city tourism.

Preserving or enhancing green spaces and their diverse uses, creating water related structures in public spaces, as well as establishing an offer of water-based sports and recreational activities and wherever possible water-based mobility, can represent valuable elements for the design of summer tourism offers in City tourism. Tourism infrastructure can bring higher living standards to a destination. Benefits can include improved infrastructure, advancements in health and transport sectors, new sports and recreational facilities, restaurants and public free spaces, enhancing the rest and retreat facility with an inundation in better-quality commodities and food.

Policy Implications –

The policy makers need a change of perspectives in their policies: focusing more on inclusive and bottom-up approach in defining the strategies. Necessary changes for a post COVID 19 recovery can be the changes of target markets, new collaborations, focus on quality tourism, technological advancements in the sector. Government should focus on policies that make optimal use of environmental resources that constitute a key element in tourism development, maintaining essential ecological processes and helping to conserve natural heritage and biodiversity. Policies ensuring viable, long term economic operations, providing socio-economic benefits to all stakeholders that are fairly distributed, including stable environment, income earning opportunities, social services to host communities and contributing to poverty alleviation. Effective policies can help in bringing tourism back on track and restoring the confidence of travellers regarding health issues,

risk of cancelled travel plans and becoming stranded overseas. It can also help to mitigate the socio-economic impacts on livelihoods.

Pro-Poor Tourism –

tourism is the third largest foreign exchange earner in India, with accounting for 10 percent of the total GDP. The tourism industry has the upper hand of occupying even the unskilled workers. Hence, the sector can help in fighting poverty, but obviously not compromising with the quality of the sector. Pro-poor tourism including the vulnerable section of the society, has also been a priority of Uttar Pradesh government's 2016 tourism policy and also India's fifth five-year plan. There are many ways to help spread benefits of tourism. In general, the poor do better when tourists spend on local products, rather than glamourizing the local market. A minimum wage can be enforced in order to make long lasting benefits with promotion of local products and more of job opportunities.

Digital Tourism –

Social media is critical in promoting cultural tourism destination, being an excellent platform to promote products such as high quality, guided, experiential tourism routes, which should characterise the cultural tourism of the future. The difficulties of movement during the pandemic and the necessary constraints on the number of visitors to cultural tourism destinations mean, and will continue to mean, that not all the potential tourists will immediately be able to travel to their desired destination and may resort to virtual visits online.

Conclusion

Travel and tourism provide a substantial contribution to business operations and ultimately contribute to the worldwide economy. The travel and tourism sector are an economic driver to the destination country's local GDP (Wondirad). The pandemic has reflected social, psychological and socio-economic and cultural influence on various tourism stakeholders, and they will suffer from the adverse effects for a longer time: the pandemic has provided an 'abundant' new framework in which tourism scholars and researchers can conduct studies with applicable research models. Tourism impact surveys need to ignore or drop the previous methods to execute the tourism and travel industry (Michael Hall). Researchers need to implement feasibility studies, tourism demand forecasting, and active and best practices that would be beneficial and appropriate to explore the COVID 19 consequences on various geographic organizations and stakeholders.

The focus should be on the increase in visitor numbers through a better more comfortable travel personalized service with maintaining affordable prices. During this low flow of tourism, policy makers should consider renovating hotels, improving staff quality and moving to digital technology. Also, attention should be paid to high quality sanitation measures. This study draws an empirical assessment for the travel and tourism industry in Varanasi. Travellers have become more selective and hence focus should be on long time trips rather than fewer trips. This pattern will reduce the negative effects of the travel industry. E-tourism can bring a definite change in the travel and tourism industry's future by providing assessable and multi-functional value structures, structural definitions, theoretical trends and substantial and flexible technical concepts.

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